

[10.5281/zenodo.13293878](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13293878)

Vol. 07 Issue 07 July - 2024

Manuscript ID: #01521

IN-SERVICE TRAINING AND EMPLOYEES' PRODUCTIVITY IN THE HOTEL INDUSTRY

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Abstract

Hotel employees in Lagos State tend to become obsolete due to organizational, technological, and social dynamics as a result of little or no attention to staff training needs. Studies that examined the link between in-service training and employees' productivity in the hotel industry in Nigeria, particularly in Lagos State, have not been reported, hence the justification for this study. The main objectives of the study are to examine the correlation between the dimensions of in-service training and employees' productivity in the hotel industry in Lagos state. Human capital theory and a quantitative research design were used. The research population comprised the 792 registered hotels in the 20 LGA in Lagos State out of which 63 hotels were selected through systematic random sampling. Taro Yamane formula was used to determine the sample size of 1,624 staffs out of 330 staffs in the selected hotels in the 20 LGAs of Lagos State. Structured questionnaires were used to collect the data, and analysed using Multiple Regression. The tested hypothetical relationship between dimensions of in-service training and employees' productivity shows that both on-the-job training and off-the-job training has positive and significant relationship with employees' productivity. It is concluded that on-the-job and off-the-job training are therapies for enhanced employees' job productivity in the hotel industry.

Keywords:

In-service training, Employees' productivity, Hotel industry, Off-the-job training, On-the-job training.

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INTRODUCTION

Corporate organisations recognise that their competitive edge in today's marketplace is entrenched in the extent of the skills acquired by their employees. It follows therefore that, for the employees in organisation to perform their duties and make meaningful contributions to the success of their organisations, the need for in-service training cannot be ruled out. In-service training is therefore needed to develop employees' skills and attitude requirements for enhanced productivity. In-service training in this context explains the systematic approach to learning and development that improve individual workers' productivity (Khawaja & Nadeem, 2013; Nda & Fard, 2013). In-service training is therefore an instrument that aids human capital in exploring their dexterity, hence vital to the productivity of the workforce in organizations. Puke (2010) affirmed that an employee who has not received adequate training before being assigned responsibilities may be lacking in necessary confidence with which different tasks are performed. As it relates to the hotel industry, hotel employees tend to become obsolete due to organizational, technological, and social dynamics including, intense competition, which resulted in increasing demand for a well-trained workforce. However, a personal experience during the exploration survey of hotel staff training needs and investment in a leadership strategic workshop organised in one of the states in the South-West, Nigeria revealed that hotel owners pay little or no attention to staff training needs. This is believed to have a far-reaching negative impact on employees' productivity. In the current study, in-service training is measured by two dimensions namely; on-the-job training, and off-the-job training (Ndidi & Moses, 2021; Karim, Choudhury & Latif, 2019).

In the last five years, the productivity of hotels in Nigeria had consistently experienced a decline despite huge investment attracted to the industry. Practically, the trend of hotel productivity outlook in Lagos State occasioned by its room occupancy (i.e. A practical non-financial index used to determine the productivity of the hotel employee) is of serious concern with the average value put at 47.44% (Statista, 2022; Jll, 2018; PricewaterhouseCoopers, 2019). This implies the physical capacity of hotel facilities in Lagos state is underutilised, hence low employee productivity. In this study, employees' productivity is viewed as a single construct with multidimensional factors. This is in conformity to Lee et al. (1999) assertion that the construct; of productivity is a function of employees' efficiency, effectiveness, and quality.

Nahavandi, Denhardt, Denhardt, and Aristigueta (2014) opined that a strong and significant relationship exists between in-service training and workers' productivity. Theoretically, reports in the extant literature revealed that various studies on the association between in-service training and employees' productivity have mainly focused on the electricity companies in Pakistan (Sabir, Aktar, Bukhari, Nasir & Ahmed, 2014), the rubber manufacturing industry in Nigeria (Eneh, Inyang, & Ekpe, 2015); mobile telephone industry in Kenya (Adongo, 2013); the insurance industry in Nigeria (Abomeh & Peace, 2015); small and medium-scale enterprises in Nigeria (Ndidi and Moses, 2021); the banking industry in Nigeria (Malaolu & Ogbuabor, 2013), and the sugar company in Kenya (Otukey, KimaniChege, & Douglas, 2013). Other studies on the link between in-service training and productivity were conducted in Dhaka, Bangladesh (Karim, Choudhury & Latif, 2019);

Kumasi, Ghana (Amoah-Mensah & Darkwa, 2016), and Uganda (Nassazi, 2013). However, studies that examined the link between in-service training and employees' productivity in the hotel industry in Nigeria, particularly in Lagos State, have not been reported. On this premise, the need to examine the relationship between the dimensions of in-service training and employees' productivity of the hotel industry in Lagos necessitates this study.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Framework: Human capital theory

The theory of Human capital was proposed in the early 1960s by an American economist, Theodore W. Schultz (Bauer & Zimmermann 1999). The theory was further shaped by Gary S. Becker, an American student of Schultz, who treated human capital as the outcome of an investment process (Block, 1990). The theory was originally used in the field of economics to explain economic performance and how wages are determined (Bauer & Zimmermann 1999). The human capital theory holds that human capital is an outcome of the investment process hence, earnings in the labour market depend upon the employees' information, skills, and level of education attainment (Becker, 1994). The theory was further used to explain labour migration (Fourage & Ester 2007; Massey et al., 1993), hence, identified human capital endowments, skills, age, marital status, gender, occupation, and labour market status as well as personal preferences and expectations of immigrants has had a strong determinant of who migrates and who does not. In addition, the human capital theory had been applied to explain the tangible and intangible factors and other important complexities that characterised the decision-making behaviour of international edu-tourists (Sarpong, 2002; Becker, 1994; Mincer, 1993a). Lately, the human capital theory has gained more prominence in the workplace. The theory argued that human capital was similar to other types of capital and could be invested in through training, and education for enhanced workers' productivity. As it applies to the current study, the theory argued that hotel organisations who invest in in-service training (i.e. on-the-job, and or off-the-job) tend to increase their worker's level of productivity. Given the applicability of this theory to this study, the theory stands to be adopted for the study.

Conceptual Clarification: In-service Training

Dale (2010) defined in-service training as the organised procedure by which people learn knowledge and skills for a definite purpose. Badeian (2009) sees in-service training as the process of developing an individual's skills, knowledge and attitude so as to improve present and future productivity. Ejiogu (2011) opined that in-service training is a process of causing a person to respond to discipline and instruction for enhanced proficiency. Grobler, Wörnich, Carrell, Elbert, and Hatfield (2011) described in-service training as the use of specific means to inculcate specific learning, using techniques that can be identified and described. Beardwell and Holden (2001) viewed in-service training as a planned process to modify attitude, knowledge, or skill behaviour through learning experience to achieve effective productivity. Reynolds (2004) defined in-service training as a set of activities that react to present needs and is focused on learning as a process of developing individual and organisational potential and building capabilities for the future instructor and contrasts. The

index in the above definitions shows that in-service training is defined as an employee development mechanism aimed at developing the abilities of the individual and satisfying the current and future needs of the organization. In-service training therefore refers to the acquisition of the skills, knowledge, and competencies required to perform a task, by means of teaching. It can also be explained as a planned and systematic effort by management aimed at altering the behaviour of employees, in a direction that will achieve organisational goals.

Definitions of Employees' Productivity

Pradhan and Jena (2016) defined employee productivity as individuals' work achievement after exerting the required effort on the job. Employee productivity is therefore defined as the employee's outcome or contributions in reference to the attainment of set goals (Viswesvaran & Ones, 2000). Employee productivity can as well be defined as the art to complete a task within defined boundaries (Igbal, Ijaz, Latif, & Mushtaq, 2015). Perrin (2016), Dhaifallah, Ebrahim, Durrishah, Raheleh, & Talalratyan (2013) defined employee productivity as an individual outcome based on the set standards in terms of accuracy, and completeness over a specified period. Gibson (2012) defined employee productivity as a measure of employee morale, and effective and efficient completion of mutually agreed tasks as set out by the employer. Employees' productivity involves recurring activities to establish organizational goals, monitor progress toward the goals, and make adjustments to achieve those goals more effectively and efficiently (Dhaifallah, et al., 2013). Platt and Sobotka (2010) defined job productivity as quality and quantity achieved by individuals or groups after fulfilling a task. Indices in these definitions show that employee productivity is the activities related to the job and how well those activities were executed by employees. Therefore, the working definition for this study describes employee productivity to connote workers' output rate and the ability to achieve tasks before the deadline, with limited error and complaint rate in line with organizational set goals.

Dimensions of In-service Training

In the current study, in-service training is measured by two dimensions namely; on-the-job training, and off-the-job training (Ndidi & Moses, 2021; Karim, Choudhur & Latif, 2019). On-the-job training involves the acquisition of skills, knowledge, and attitudes by employees from their superiors (Abdiwali & Musa, 2019). It is often planned, structured, and carried out at the trainee's workplace with a focus on the teaching of specific skills and knowledge on the job (Aswathappa, 2002). On-the-job training programs are sometimes carried out in a special on-site training area, hence including, orientation training, job instruction training, apprenticeship training, internships and assistantships, job rotation, and coaching (Nassazi, 2013). On-the-job training is recommended to managers because this has been found to be more associated with employees' performance. Off-the-job training on the other hand refers to training conducted off-the-site of the organisation. Off-the-job training is usually designed to meet the shared learning needs of a group rather than a particular individual's needs (Phoeth 2017). Off-the-job training can involve group discussions, one-to-one tutorials, lectures, reading, training courses and workshops (Aswathappa, 2002). Off-the-job training needs to be provided when employees lack the skills or information to work

productively when the right resources exist to draw up, impart, and follow up the training and when training resolves performance problems. It is worthwhile providing off-the-job training when a large number of staff have a similar training requirement and when there are adequate skills and resources for the design and provision of training (Rothwell&Kazanas, 2004).

Measures of Employees' Productivity

In this study, employees' productivity is viewed as a single construct though with multidimensional factors. This is in conformity to Lee et al. (1999) assertion that the construct of productivity is a function of employees' efficiency, effectiveness, and quality. Employees' efficiency is seen as the achievement of specified tasks against predetermined or identified standards of accuracy, completeness, cost, and speed (Sabir, Iqbal, Rehman, Shah, &Yameen, 2012).Efficiency also refers to the employee's output rate and ability to accomplish tasks before the deadline (Afshan, Sobia, Kamran, &Nasir, 2012).Effectiveness refers to the employee's goal accomplishment rate and proposals (Rana &Singh, 2016a; Lee et al., 1999). Effectiveness therefore could be said to be the ability of an employee to accomplish his or her mission based on the expectations of an organisation (Perrin, 2016).Quality refers to the employee's error and complaint rate, supervisor, customer and colleague satisfaction rate (Bello &Majebi, 2018).It emphasized the number of customer complaints handled, the number of repeat customers, and the quality of customer services as well as change/improvement in job skill level (Tsai, Cheng,&Chang, 2010).

Empirical Review and Hypothesis Development

Relationship between on-the-job training, and employees' productivity

A critical review of literature affirmed that studies on the association between on-the-job training and employees' productivity mainly focused on the electricity companies in Pakistan (Sabir, Aktar, Bukhari, Nasir &Ahmed, 2014), mobile telephone industry in Kenya (Adongo, 2013); the insurance industry in Nigeria (Abomeh & Peace, 2015); small and medium-scale enterprises in Nigeria (Ndidi &Moses, 2021); the banking industry in Nigeria (Malaolu &Ogbuabor, 2013), and the sugar company in Kenya (Otuke, KimaniChege, &Douglas, 2013). Other studies conducted in this domain were conducted in Dhaka, Bangladesh (Karim, Choudhur &Latif, 2019); Kumasi, Ghana (Amoah-Mensah &Darkwa, 2016), and Uganda (Nassazi, 2013).This implies that limited studies have been carried out in this domain concerning the hotel industry in Nigeria and in particular in Lagos State. The key issue here is that hotel managers in Lagos state did not realise the impact of on-the-job training on employees' productivity which ultimately results in critical managerial dilemmas. In view of this, we tend to assume the subsequent hypothesis:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between on-the-job training and employees' productivity in the hotel industry in Lagos State.

Relationship between off-the-job training and employees' productivity

Studies on the link between off-the-job training and employees' productivity were conducted in the context of electricity companies in Pakistan (Sabir, Aktar, Bukhari, Nasir & Ahmed, 2014), the rubber manufacturing industries in Nigeria (Eneh, Inyang &Ekpe, 2015); mobile

telephone industries in Kenya (Adongo, 2013); insurance industries in Nigeria (Abomeh & Peace, 2015); small and medium-scale enterprises in Nigeria (Ndidi & Moses, 2021); banking industries in Nigeria (Malaolu & Ogbuabor, 2013), and a sugar company in Kenya (Otuke, KimaniChege, & Douglas, 2013); judiciary in Nairobi Kenya (Ngari, 2015); The Nigeria Agip Oil Company, Port Harcourt (Badom & Girigiri, 2021); The Nigerian bottling companies (Adelere, 2017) and The Vita Foam Nigeria plc (Aminu, 2011). This implies that limited studies have been carried out to investigate the link between off-the-job training and employees’ productivity in the hotel industry in Nigeria and in particular in Lagos State. The fact that hotel employees in Lagos state tend to become obsolete due to environmental dynamics, and hence tend to perform poorly calls for this study to examine the association between off-the-job training and employees’ productivity in the hotels in Lagos state. In view of this, we tend to assume the subsequent hypothesis:

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between off-the-job training and employees’ productivity in the hotel industry in Lagos State.

Operational Framework

To achieve the objectives of this study, in-servicetraining and employees’ productivity model (In-EP Model) for the hotel industry in Lagos State were proposed as shown in Figure 1. The In-HEP model comprises of an independent variable with two dimensions which include: On-the- job training (Abdiwali & Musa, 2019; Nassazi, 2013), and Off-the-job training (Phoeth 2017; Rothwell, 2005).The dependent variable for the study; employees’ productivity was used as a uni-dimensional construct. The In-HEP model is therefore expected to explain the relationship between the two dimensions of in-service training and the dependent variable (i.e. Employees’ productivity) in respect to hotels in Lagos State Nigeria.

Figure 1: In-service Training and Hotel Employees’ Productivity (In- HEP) Model
 Source: Researchers Conception (2024).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a quantitative research design, hence, the researchers used structured questionnaire to determine the correlation between dimensions of in-service training and employees' productivity of hotels in Lagos State. The population comprises employees of the 792 registered hotels in the 20 Local Government Areas of Lagos State out of which employees of 63 of the registered hotels were used as the sampling units. The 63 sampled hotels were selected through a systematic random sampling technique, hence the researchers serially numbered all the 792 registered hotels in the 20 LGAs in Lagos State, and automatically picked the first hotel on the list in each of the LGAs while others were picked at an interval of 15. Thus, the employees of the 63 selected hotels put at 1, 624 formed the unit of analysis of the study. Since it is practically impossible for the researchers to sample the entire 1, 624 employees in the 63 selected hotels in the 20 LGAs in Lagos State, hence Taro Yamane formula based on proportional allocation was used to determine the sample size of the study put at 330 employees.

The instrument used for this study is divided into 3 parts. Part 1 of the questionnaire provides the personal information of the respondents. Part 2 of the questionnaire comprises of two dimensions of in-service training which include: On-the-Job Training: The instrument of on-the-job training used in this study was adapted from the job training and job satisfaction survey technical manual of the East Carolina University. The instrument which consists of 46 items was developed by Steven (2004). For the current study, 6 items of the instrument were modified and used on a 5-point likert scale of 1 representing strongly disagree to 5 representing strongly agreed with respect to hotels in Lagos State. Off-the-Job Training: A 25-items off-the-job training scale developed by Akther, Tariq and Islam (2019) was adapted for the current study. The modified scale that consists of 7 items used to measure off-the-job training with respect to the current study. Each items were measured on a 5-point Likert scale, with 1 representing strongly disagree and 5 representing strongly agreed with respect to hotels in Lagos State. Part 3 of the questionnaire measured employees' productivity. Employees' Productivity six items instrument developed by Lee et al. (1999) was adopted and modified based on job performance literature in Sahin (2011) and Motowidlo and Van Scotter (1994). The modified instrument consists of 8 items and measured on a 5-point Likert scale. Each items were rated by the respondents from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agreed). To validate the research instrument, copy of the scale was given to experts for validation and rewording of items of the constructs. A pilot test was conducted to determine the reliability of the instrument. The instrument was pre-tested on 100 staff of the selected hotels in Lagos State. The reliability test for each of the two constructs in the instrument were examined for its Cronbach's alpha, and composite reliability with acceptable threshold of > 0.7 as suggested in (Hair et al., 2006) and shown in Table 1.

Table 1: The Results of the Reliability Test

Observed Variables / Items	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
ON THE JOB TRAINING	.841	
The on-the-job training I received is applicable to my job.	.827	
The training i received on-the-job meets my current job needs and prepares me for future positions.	.795	
I am satisfied with the quality of training I received on the job.	.814	
I am generally able to use what I learnt in on-the-job training in my job.	.814	
I view on-the-job training as a continuous and lifelong endeavor.	.844	
On-the-job training is planned and purposeful in my organisation rather than accidental.	.795	
OFF-THE-JOB TRAINING		.843
Off-the-job training helped me to acquire knowledge and skills related to my job.	.850	
Off-the-job training gave adequate importance to developing my skills and competence.	.808	
All the logistics supports were available during the off-the-job training.	.806	
I am assertive that knowledge impacted through off-the-job training would improve my confidence at work.	.797	
Off-the-job training methods are encouraged and rewarded in my organisation.	.820	
My organization is proactive in seeking off-the-job training ways to improve what I do.	.815	
I perceived off-the-job training have learning goals designed to enhance my current work assignment.	.851	
JOB PRODUCTIVITY		.815
I create effective work relationship with others.	.803	
I find effective solutions to problems.	.784	
I contribute to my current organization in terms submitting new ideas.	.780	
I strive to meet deadlines.	.786	
I adapt easily to changing situations.	.785	
I encourage colleagues to do more than what is expected.	.801	
I assume a sense of ownership and responsibility in the quality of personal performance.	.806	
I strive to give undivided attention while discharging my duties.	.804	

Source: Researcher's Computation (2024).

Descriptive statistics was used to analyse questionnaire distribution and respondents' demographics characteristics using statistical package for social science (SPSS) software version 23. Multiple regressions were used to evaluate the relationship between dimensions of in-service training and employees' productivity in respect to hotels in Lagos State.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Questionnaire distribution information

A total of 330 questionnaires were distributed by the researchers with the support of research assistants to the target respondents in the 63 hotels in the 20 LGAs in Lagos State. Interestingly, all the 330 questionnaires that was administered were filled and returned, giving a response rate of 100%.

Respondents' demographic profile

Table 2 shows the summary of the demographic features of the respondents of the study.

Table 2: The Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Profile	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Marital Status		
1. Single	220	66.7
2. Married	107	32.4
3. Divorce	3	.9
Religion		
1. Islam	232	70.3
2. Christianity	51	15.5
3. Others	47	14.2
Age		
1. 17-26	175	53.0
2. 27-35	109	33.0
3. 36-44	44	13.3
4. 45 and above	2	0.60
Educational Qualification		
1. HND / B.Sc	116	35.2
2. PGD.	105	31.8
3. M.Sc.	109	33.0
Gender		
1. Male	207	62.7
2. Female	123	37.3

Source: Researcher's Computation (2024).

From the Table 2, the result of the demographic characteristics of the respondents show that 220 of the respondents are single (66.7%) while 107 are married (32.4%). The frequency of the divorced is 3 representing .9%. This implies that the majority of the participants in this study are singles. The religions' distribution of respondents is; Christianity (15.5%) Islam, (70.3%), and Others, (14.2%). This shows that the majority of participants in the study are Muslims while Christians and Others follows. The age distribution of respondents reveals that the participants between the ages of 17-26 are the largest group, comprising 175 participants (53.0%). The analysis further shows that about 109 respondents (33.0%) are between the age of 27- 35, while those ages 36-44 are 44 (13.3%) while 45-above years of age are 2 (.6%). This shows that the majority of the participants used for this study have their age range within 17-26 years, followed by those with age bracket 27-35. Analysis of participant's distribution by education qualification shows that about 116 of the respondents have Higher National Diploma (HND) / B.Sc.put at 35.2%. About 105 of the respondents have PGD put at 31.8% while 109 of the respondents have M.Sc (33.0%). This implies that majority of the participants used in this study are holders of Higher National Diploma (HND) / B.Sc, followed by those with M.Sc Degrees. The implication of this is that employee of the hotel industry are persons of high education attainment contrary to general assumption that hotel

workers are people of low academic qualification achievement. The results of the analysis of the respondents by gender show that 207 of the respondents (62.7%) are male while 123 of the respondents (37.3%) are female. This implies that the majority of the respondents used in the study are male.

Bivariate analysis

To determine the relationship between dimensions of in-service training and employees’ productivity in the hotel industry in Lagos State, two hypotheses (H_{01} and H_{02}) in a component of the In-HEP Model as shown in Figure 1 were tested and the results of the analysis are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Correlations of In-service Training and Employees’ Productivity

Variables	R	P	Level	Hypothesis
Employees’ Productivity (EJP)	-	-	-	-
On the Job Training (OJT)	0.351	0.000	Low	$H_A = \text{Accepted}$
Off the Job Training (OFT)	0.378	0.000	Low	$H_A = \text{Accepted}$

**Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2024).

The results as shown in Table 3 depicted that the two measures of In-service Training have a positive and significant relationship with Employees’ Productivity in respect to hotels in Lagos State. Thus, On the Job Training (OJT) ($r = 0.351$; $p = 0.000$); and Off the Job Training (OFT) ($r = 0.378$; $p = 0.000$). In terms of the strength of the relationship, the results show that On the Job Training (OJT); and Off the Job Training (OFT) have low correlation with employees’ Productivity in respect of hotels in Lagos State.

Table 4: Model Summary of In-service Training and Employees’ Productivity

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.456 ^a	.208	.203	4.25911	.208	42.885	2	327	.000

a. Dependent Variable: EJP

b. Predictors: (Constant), OFT, OJT

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2024).

From Table 4, it was observed that the R-square for the model is .208 which implies that the two dimensions of in-service training explained 20.8% of the variance in employees’ productivity in respect to hotels in Lagos State. Therefore, the remaining 79.2% is due to other factors and residuals. Also, the multiple R ($R = .456$) revealed a significant high relationship between independent variables (i.e. dimensions of in-service training) and the dependent variable (employees’ productivity).

Table 5: ANOVA^a In-service Training and Employees' Productivity

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1555.864	2	777.932	42.885	.000 ^b
	Residual	5931.788	327	18.140		
	Total	7487.652	329			

a. Dependent Variable: EJP.

b. Predictors: (Constant), OFT, OJT

Source: Researcher's Computation (2024).

Table 5 indicates that the result of the analysis shows that F value is significant (F= 42,885, p=.000). This shows that the model is valid. Thus, based on the findings it can be concluded that there is a linear relationship between the dimensions of in-service training and employees' productivity of hotels in Lagos State.

Table 6:Coefficients^aContribution of In-service Training and Employees' Productivity

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Correlations		
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Zero-order	Partial	Part
		1	(Constant)	12.764			1.761		7.247	.000	9.299
	OJT	.147	.073	.115	2.022	.044	.004	.291	.309	.111	.100
	OFT	.435	.064	.387	6.800	.000	.309	.560	.445	.352	.335

a. Dependent Variable: EJP

b. Predictors: (Constant), OFT, OJT

Source: Researcher's Computation (2024).

In differentiating the contribution of each independent variable, Beta values are used. As illustrated in the standardized coefficient column in Table 6, Off-the-job training (OFT) has the highest contributions put at (.389) to employees' productivity, followed by On-the-job training (OJT) (.115).

Discussion of findings

The objective of this study examined the relationship dimensions of in-service training and employees' productivity of hotels in Lagos State. The results of this study revealed that a positive and significant relationship exists between in-service training and employees' productivity. The outcome of this study conform to the previous studies. Extent literature shown that employees are better productive when they are encouraged to participation in on-the-job training (Nassazi, 2013; Malaolu & Ogbuabor, 2013). This was further confirmed in Bafaneli and Setibi (2015) who assessed the impact of on-the-job training on employees' performance in Riley's Hotel, Botswana and the study shows that on-the-job training significantly and positively impacts employees' productivity. Ndunguru (2015) also

examined the impact of on-the-job training on employees' performance: the case of secondary school teachers of Songea municipality, Tanzania. The study discovered that employee training has a significant relationship with employees' productivity. Al-Mzary, Al-Rifai, and Al-Momany (2015) examined the link between in-service training and employees' performance in Malaysian small and medium enterprises (SMEs). Results of the study indicated that there is a positive and significant relationship between in-service training and employees' job productivity. Falola, Osibanjo, and Ojo (2014) studied the effectiveness of training on employees' productivity in selected banks in Lagos, Nigeria. The results of the study showed that a strong, positive and significant relationship exists between in-service training and employees' productivity.

In addition, this study also shows that a positive and significant relationship exists between off-the-job training and employees' productivity hence, confirm to outcome of previous studies. Oladipo and Adebayo (2021) examined the link between off-the-job training on employees' performance in manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The result of the study showed a positive and significant relationship between off-the-job training and employees' productivity. Ogbu and Osanaiye (2017) examined the impact of employees' training on employees' productivity in insurance firms in Abuja, Nigeria. The study established that off-the-job training has a significant relationship with employees' productivity in the insurance industry in Abuja. Other studies that were reviewed in respect of the relationship between off-the-job training and employees' productivity were conducted in the context of electricity companies in Pakistan (Sabir, Aktar, Bukhari, Nasir & Ahmed, 2014), the rubber manufacturing industries in Nigeria (Eneh, Inyang, & Ekpe, 2015); mobile telephone industries in Kenya (Adongo, 2013); insurance industries in Nigeria (Abomeh and Peace, 2015); small and medium-scale enterprises in Nigeria (Ndidi & Moses, 2021); banking industries in Nigeria (Malaolu & Ogbuabor, 2013), and a sugar company in Kenya (Otuke, KimaniChege, & Douglas, 2013).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions from the findings

Congruently, in accordance with the In-EM Model used for this study, research objectives, and hypothesis predictions were developed in agreement with previous literature that examined the contributions of various constructs towards explaining the relationship between the constructs in the context of hotels in Lagos State. Fortunately, answers to these research objectives have been found; and all the proposed hypotheses investigated were found to be supported. It is therefore critical to state that on-the-job training and off-the-job training in hotels in Lagos business environment would sustainably enhances employees' productivity. It is concluded that managers of hotel establishment should put in place policy thrust that would ensure conducive in-service training for enhanced staff productivity.

Recommendations

Despite the insightful results that were obtained, the study still has some limitations. One of the limitations of this study is that only hotels in Lagos State were used. The unit of analysis

and the sampled population could be increased and extended to other states in Nigeria hence, tend to provides better information and results. The researchers therefore recommend that future studies should replicate the outcome of the study in other States in Nigeria. One of the limitations of the current study is that only the staff of hotels in Lagos was focused, thus did not consider the perception of the impact of employees' productivity from the customers' perspective. In view of this, the researchers recommend that future studies should increase the dimensions of in-service training, increase the unit of analysis, and extent the study to other states of the federation for better and insightful information and results.

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